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**Expanding Long Term Financing Options for Middle-income Countries in Latin
America and Caribbean with High HIV Burden**

A Case Study from Ecuador

Draft Submitted by

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Abstract

A model was developed to project future demand and supply of financing for Ecuador's HIV/AIDS programs under different scenarios over a 15 year period, from 2009 to 2023. The exercise reveals that in all likelihood Ecuador will face large and growing funding gaps in the future, and that new funding sources, or a growing fiscal effort by government, or sustained or greater financial support from donors will be required to bridge such gaps.

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Acronyms

AIDS	Acquired immune deficiency syndrome
ARV	Antiretroviral therapy
BSS	Behavioral surveillance survey
CBO	Community Based Organizations
CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, DHSS (USA)
CSW	Commercial sex worker
DHS	Demographic health survey
H(M)IS	Health (Management) Information System
HIV	Human immunodeficiency virus
IDU	Injecting drug user
IEC	Information, education, communication
IPT	Intermittent preventive treatment
IRS	Indoor residual spraying
KAP	Knowledge, Attitude and Practice
M&E	Monitoring and evaluation
MARP	Most-at-risk population (female sex workers, clients of female sex workers, injecting drug users and men who have sex with men)
MDG	Millennium Development Goal
METAT	Monitoring and Evaluation Technical Assistance and Training
MICS	Multiple Indicator Cluster Surveys
MOH	Ministry of Public Health
MSM	Men who have sex with men
NAP	National AIDS Program
NASA	National AIDS Spending Assessment
NGO	Non-governmental organization
ODA	Official development assistance
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
OGAC	The President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief: Office of the Global AIDS Coordinator
OVC	Orphans and vulnerable children
PEPFAR	President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief (USA)
PLWHA	People living with HIV/AIDS
PMTCT	Prevention of Mother-to-Child Transmission (of HIV)
PPM	Public-private mix
PSI	Population Services International
RNM	Resource needs model
SDA	Service delivery area
STI	Sexually transmitted infections
SW	Sex Workers
UNGASS	UN General Assembly Special Session
UNDP	United Nations Development Program
VCT	Voluntary counseling and testing

1. Introduction

The worldwide HIV/AIDS epidemic reached its peak in 1996, when 3.5 million new infections were reported, compared with 30 percent fewer new cases being reported in 2008. However, the number of people living with HIV/AIDS (PLWHA) worldwide continued to grow in 2008, reaching an estimated 33.4 million, due to the number of new cases reported and the increase in life expectancy of people living with HIV/AIDS. The total number of PLWHA in 2008 was 20 percent higher than in 2000, and three times as high as in 1990 (UNAIDS, 2009a).

In 2008 the adult prevalence of HIV/AIDS in Latin American was 0.6 percent, below the global prevalence of 0.8 percent; conversely, in the Caribbean prevalence was higher at 1.0 percent. The Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) region as a whole reported a prevalence that was well below that of sub-Saharan Africa (5.2 percent) (UNAIDS, 2009a). Half of adults living with the virus are women. The latest epidemiological data suggest that the epidemic in Latin America remains stable.

The majority of countries in the region have prevalence rates of less than 1 percent, but the prevalence among specific groups, such as men who have sex with men (MSM) and sex workers (SW), is often very high. The most severe expressions of the epidemic occur in smaller countries such as Belize, Guyana, and Suriname, with prevalence ranging between 2.1 and 2.5 percent. For example, in the Bahamas and Haiti more than 2 percent of the adult population is living with HIV/AIDS. Higher prevalence rates are found only in sub-Saharan Africa, making the Caribbean the second-most affected region in the world. Table 1 depicts the situation of the epidemic in terms of the estimated number of PLWHA, deaths and lethality rate in selected Latin America and Caribbean countries.

Table 1 People living with HIV/AIDS and deaths from this cause in LAC region, circa 2006

Country	Living with HIV/AIDS (LWHA)		Estimated deaths due to HIV/AIDS, 2007	Lethality: Number of deaths/ Number of PLWHA (%)
	All people	Adult (15-49) rate %		
Brazil	730,000	0.6	15,000	2.1
Costa Rica	9,700	0.4	<200	2.1
Chile	31,000	0.3	<1,000	3.2
Average Latin America	1,700,000	0.5	63,000	3.7
Peru	76,000	0.5	3,300	4.3
Argentina	120,000	0.5	5,400	4.5
Ecuador	26,000	0.3	1,200	4.6
Paraguay	21,000	0.6	<1,000	4.8
El Salvador	35,000	0.8	1,700	4.9
Panama	20,000	1.0	<1,000	5.0
Uruguay	10,000	0.6	<500	5.0
Mexico	200,000	0.3	11,000	5.5
Belize	3,600	2.1	<200	5.6
Colombia	170,000	0.6	9,800	5.8
Bolivia	8,100	0.2	<500	6.2
Haiti	120,000	2.2	7,500	6.3
Dominican Republic	62,000	1.1	3,900	6.3
Honduras	28,000	0.7	1,800	6.4
Nicaragua	7,700	0.2	<500	6.5
Guatemala	59,000	0.8	3,900	6.6
Guyana	13,000	2.5	<1,000	7.7

Source: UNAIDS (2008).

According to the World Bank (2003), worldwide concern over the HIV/AIDS epidemic responds to its triple impact on society:

- It destroys human capital, including accumulated life experience, job skills and knowledge.
- It weakens the mechanisms that generate human capital information, damaging the transmission of knowledge and potential productive capacity across generations.
- It makes investment in the education of children less attractive given the prospect that they may get infected, even if both parents remain uninfected.

A country's ability to fight the epidemic critically depends on the amount of resources it can mobilize to prevent and treat cases. Hence countries should establish the importance of measuring financing needs and resources availability. Success factors in managing the HIV/AIDS epidemic include:

- The existence of national health care organizations.
- The availability and allocation of public funds.
- The availability and allocation of international funds.
- The presence and strength of national initiatives and organization around HIV/AIDS.

LAC countries have, with few exceptions (most notably Brazil), chosen the social security approach to achieve universal health care coverage. But a high prevalence of poverty, unemployment, and informal employment has restricted social security coverage to the relatively small share of the population in the formal sector of the economy. Given the epidemiological dynamics of the HIV/AIDS epidemic, it is expected that there will be an increasing demand for fresh resources each year. Social security institutions typically do not have enough resources to deal with the epidemic and therefore additional public, private, and international resources are necessary.

Despite resource limitations, the regional coverage of curative and preventive care for HIV/AIDS is relatively high in LAC compared with the rest of the developing world. UNAIDS (2009a) reports the following:

Antiretroviral coverage in Latin America (at 54% in 2008) is above the global average, with especially high coverage achieved in several upper-middle-income countries (World Health Organization, United Nations Children's Fund, UNAIDS, 2009). In general, treatment coverage is higher in South America than in Central America.

This report looks at the financing of HIV/AIDS interventions in Ecuador, a country with an adult prevalence rate of 0.3 percent –a relatively low figure for regional standards. In 2008 per capita income in Ecuador, measured in international dollars, was US\$ 8,008, below the LAC average of US\$ 10,159. UNAIDS (2009c) summarizes the economic and HIV/AIDS situation in Ecuador as follows:

- An economy that is highly dependent on oil exports and therefore one that is highly vulnerable to external shocks and changes in oil prices, such as during the 2007-2008 world financial crisis.
- A prevalence of HIV/AIDS of between 0.1 and 0.5 percent, low for international standards, although it has been increasing in recent years as a result of more effective reporting methods of the disease.
- The financing of the national response is currently highly dependent on public funding. The government increased substantially the allocation of resources to the health sector

over the last three years strengthening prevention, treatment and program management for HIV/AIDS.

- The enactment of a new Constitution in 2008 that guarantees the right to free and comprehensive health care for all citizens regardless of their beliefs, sexual orientation, or HIV condition resulted in a legal framework that forced the public health services to respond to the needs of the population, accordingly.
- The Inter-American Commission on Human Rights (IACHR), in 2002, granted precautionary measures on behalf of six PLWHA. The petitioners argued, inter alia, that State health agencies had failed to provide the beneficiaries with basic testing to determine the course of the disease as well as adequate treatment. The Commission requested that the State provide the beneficiaries with the medical examination and treatment indispensable for their survival (<http://www.cidh.oas.org/medidas/2002.eng.htm>). Since then the government of Ecuador through the Ministry of Health had strengthened its response to HIV/AIDS by increasing preventive measures, improving diagnosis and treatment, and developing an appropriate information system.
- The importance of the contribution of external funding, in particular, from the Global Fund to the national HIV/AIDS response has decreased proportionally to the sustained increase of public funding since 2007.

Whereas prevalence of HIV/AIDS in Ecuador is lower than average, the coverage of ARV, at 39 percent in 2009, was below the regional average (UNAIDS, 2009c), although it has improved from 29.8 percent in 2007. Securing adequate financing, both domestically and internationally, to fund the HIV/AIDS national response in Ecuador is a priority both for the government and international agencies supporting this field, such as UNAIDS.

2. Study goal, objectives, and products

The goal of this study is to insinuate a sustainable long term financial strategy to respond to the HIV/AIDS epidemic in Latin American countries. This document endeavors to examine the financial feasibility of the HIV/AIDS programs and interventions in Ecuador. It is hoped that the lessons drawn from this country report may help other developing countries develop their own long-term financing strategy.

Report objectives are as follows:

- Identify existing financing sources for the Ecuador's national HIV/AIDS program.
- Gather the program's service delivery objectives, both for preventive and curative interventions, and also the coverage and access to HIV/AIDS care.
- Estimate resource needs for 2018-2023 in a range between a low and a high scenario.
- Calculate the potential gap in relation to needs and required expenditure.
- Recommend sustainable measures to meet financing needs.
- Estimate the economic impact on the country.
- Identify best practices and / or innovative financing mechanisms that could be adapted in other regions.

The methodology used in this case study is the same developed for the Dominican Republic.

This report focuses on designing a model for demand and supply of funding for HIV/AIDS in Ecuador and on determining any future gaps in financing for the period 2010-2023. These results will be presented to decision makers in the country to generate a debate regarding the feasibility of implementation for the proposed scenarios and the identification of new funding sources to fill any of the projected gaps.

3. Literature review

Projecting the costs and funding for HIV/AIDS response poses several methodological problems, three of which are considered particularly relevant for this effort and are therefore addressed in this section. First, the epidemiological data from various sources show disparate results, which mean an additional difficulty in the identification of the necessary resources related to the demand scenarios.

Second, there is international evidence that the epidemic may affect a country's present and future income flow, and that this may undermine the country's ability to collect taxes and finance social programs, such as HIV/AIDS. If this were to happen in Ecuador, then a model that projects public financing into the future should take into account the relationship between the epidemic and income, and the associated future drop in public funds resulting from the epidemic. Third, the projection of costs of preventive and curative interventions must reflect the behavior of costs as coverage expands over time. It may be the case that as coverage expands of some HIV/AIDS (for example, the delivery of ARV) total costs would increase but less than proportionally owing to possible economies of scale in the purchase and delivery of these drugs. Other interventions may also face economies of scale, or diseconomies of scale, where total costs increase more than proportionally with coverage. Third, the efficiency of delivery may improve or worsen with time. For example, current management costs may be reduced to more efficient levels that are consistent with the international practice, or the procurement of input, such as condoms, may be made more transparent through international tenders, hence lowering their unit cost.

It is important to take these three effects into account when developing the model to project future costs and financing. What follows is a review of the international literature on these issues.

3.1. The social and economic costs of HIV/AIDS

The prospect that the HIV/AIDS epidemic may affect economic growth is a central concern in this study which projects the future needs and availability of financing for HIV/AIDS interventions. If higher disease prevalence lowers economic output then it may negatively affect government tax revenue and its ability to finance social programs, such as the prevention and treatment of HIV/AIDS. If such a downward spiral exists, then an economic forecast model should take it into account to predict with accuracy the future availability of government financing. Haacker (2009) clearly explains this as follows:

The most visible fiscal consequences of HIV/AIDS include increased spending on prevention, care, and treatment, but the fiscal implications go far beyond this. As economic growth declines, the domestic tax base weakens and domestic revenues fall.

Will the countries that are the subject of the present study – the Dominican Republic, Ecuador and Guatemala– experience, as a consequence of HIV/AIDS, a future drop in economic growth? And will such a drop significantly reduce the tax base and therefore the availability of government revenue to finance interventions in health in general, in HIV/AIDS in particular, and in other social programs?

Several studies have estimated the long-term consequences of the HIV/AIDS epidemic on economic growth. Their findings may shed some light on this issue in the case of Latin America and the Caribbean. UNAIDS (2004) Haacker (2009), and Stover and Bollinger (1999) summarize the results from several of them.

While all of these authors mention that the empirical evidence is mixed and at times contradictory, they gather results from different studies and conclude that with all probability there is a negative relationship between the extent of the epidemic and economic growth. Figure 1 presents selected results in the form of an estimated interval per country or group of countries from sub-Saharan Africa. It shows that in Botswana the epidemic could be responsible for an annual drop in per capita income varying from a low of 0.8 percent to a high as 1.6 percent. For a group of 30 countries from the region, the annual drop in per capita income would be between zero percent (no impact) and 0.6 percent.

The influence of the HIV/AIDS epidemic on economic output no doubt increases with its severity, although the exact relationship cannot easily be established empirically. In 2004 the HIV/AIDS prevalence in Botswana was as high as 25 percent, the highest among the countries included in the above figure. The estimated impact on economic growth was also highest for that country. Around the same year the average prevalence for the group of 30 sub-Saharan countries was about 3 percent. For these countries, over 1992, it was estimated that the influence of the epidemic on economic growth was an annual reduction as high as 0.6 percent.

Figure 1 Selected countries from Sub-Saharan Africa: Annual drop in per capita GNP attributable to HIV/AIDS epidemic (percent)

Source: UNAIDS (2004), Haacker (2009), Over (1992), Stover and Bollinger (1999).

Figure 2 Selected countries from sub-Saharan African and Latin America: HIV/AIDS prevalence population ages 15-49 (%)

Countries from Latin America and the Caribbean exhibit HIV/AIDS prevalence rates that are generally much lower than those of countries in sub-Saharan Africa. This can be seen in Figure 2. Prevalence in the study countries varies from a low of 0.19 percent in Ecuador to a high of 0.63 percent in the Dominican Republic. It is therefore expected that in the countries selected for the current study any detrimental consequences of HIV/AIDS on economic output and public finances will be very low, if any. Therefore it does not seem necessary to model such an effect, because of its small expected magnitude, and it may not be possible to do so because the empirical estimates available in the literature come from countries with very different expressions of the epidemic.

But the HIV/AIDS epidemic has economic and social consequences that go beyond the loss of output. In the document "The economic costs of AIDS", based mainly on the situation of African countries, the World Bank Group (2003) discusses the loss of human capital resulting from the epidemic. It states that most studies about the macro-economic consequences of HIV/AIDS attempt to measure the impact as a reduction of GDP but fail to address one of the main factors affecting economic growth, namely human capital. HIV/AIDS affects economic growth by the devastating combination of several factors that destroy human capital. As a disease mainly of young adults, it selectively destroys human capital by wiping out their life experience, work skills, and knowledge gained over the years. It also weakens and reduces human capital formation mechanisms. Specifically, the death of one or both parents of young children weakens the transmission of knowledge and the joint productive capacity of families. Additionally, the drop in income that follows the death of one parent or both of them reduces the amount of resources available for the education of surviving children. Furthermore, the possibility that children will get the disease in adulthood makes investment in their education less attractive. With less education and knowledge transmitted from parents to children, as well as deprivation of love and guidance from childhood, the children of HIV/AIDS victims who later become adults are less able to raise their own children and invest in their education. The effects of this process are only noticeable over the long-term and poor education of children today results in low productivity of the adult a generation later.

It falls beyond the scope and possibilities of the current study to model the economic and social consequences just discussed. In judging the various results, however, it is important to keep these consequences in mind.

3.2. Economies of scale in the production and delivery of HIV/AIDS interventions

The current exercise involves the projection over time, through the year 2023, of the costs of curative and preventive interventions, both individual and collective, to deal with HIV/AIDS in Ecuador. It is difficult to project future costs of health services, even if one knows with some certainty what will be the future volume of services to be delivered. For example, suppose that the government had plans to double by the year 2023, to 80 percent, the current coverage of 40 percent of ARVs. Given the large share of HIV/AIDS spending accounted for by ARV therapy in the country, it is crucial to predict what will be the future resource needs of this important cost item as future coverage expands. Will the total costs of ARVs also double along with coverage? Or will total costs grow more than proportionally or less than proportionally with coverage? To answer these questions it is useful to look at past costs and their relationship with coverage in the country, to check, for example, whether the increase of coverage, from 20 percent to 40 percent,

resulted in more or less the same proportion in spending. Also, projecting future costs requires knowledge about the future costs of inputs (will pharmaceutical companies raise or lower the prices of ARVs? Will they provide further volume discounts?), the future costs of management (Will management costs of the ARV procurement facility have to double when coverage doubles? Will staff salaries increase annually irrespective of coverage?), and other future costs.

The international evidence on the economies of scale in the delivery of ARVs should, in principle, help predict what could happen to total costs in Ecuador as coverage of ARVs expands. Evidence from Nigeria and Brazil, is presented in Figure 3 and Figure 4 below. Kombe *et al.* (no date, around 2007, Figure 3 examined the cost structure of ARV programs in Nigeria, including the costs of human resources, medicines, monitoring tests, and capital and training. Their aim was to predict future variations in costs associated with coverage expansion. Thus, their study was prospective. They concluded that a considerable expansion in coverage would more or less maintain average cost per patient covered constant, at around US\$ 700 per covered patient per year.

Nunn *et al.* (2007) carried out a retrospective study to explain the variation in total and average costs of Brazil's universal and publicly funded ARV program. They found that between 2001 and 2004 the average annual cost per patient covered dropped considerably, from US\$ 1,945 to US\$ 1,297, but then it doubled through the next year (Figure 4). The number of patients covered, increased throughout the period. The major driver of cost increases in Brazil was increased purchase quantities of six specific patented drugs and a locally produced generic. A decline in prices for many of the patented drugs that constitute the largest share of drug costs meant that nearly the entire increase in overall drug expenditures between 2001 and 2005 was attributable to increases in drug quantities. Had all drug quantities been held constant from 2001 until 2005, total costs would have increased by only an estimated US\$7 million. In the absence of price declines for patented drugs, Brazil would have spent over twice as much, or US\$2 billion on ARV drugs between 2001 and 2005, implying a savings of US\$1.2 billion from price declines. They also found that Brazilian prices for locally produced generic ARVs were generally much higher than the lowest international prices meeting global pharmaceutical quality standards. The prices of Brazil's locally produced generics had risen in Brazil while declining globally. As a consequence, Brazil had spent an excess US\$ 110 million by producing local generics instead of purchasing them in international markets.

Figure 3 Nigeria: Patients receiving ARVs and average annual cost of ARVs per patient , year 2007 and projected

Source: Kombe *et al.* (circa 2007).

Figure 4 Brazil: Patients receiving highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART) and average annual cost of ARVs per patient , 1997-2006

Source: Nunn *et al.* (2007).

When the average cost *per unit of output* (for example, per patient receiving ARV therapy) drops as output expands, economists say that they are in the presence of *economies of scale*. That is a desirable situation from the perspective of financing, because each person covered, or each unit of service delivered, will *on average* cost less. So a doubling of coverage will result in less than a doubling in the associated costs. This implies that the larger the program, the smaller the amount of resources that will be required to pay for each person covered, or patient seen, or output delivered.

Kumaranayake (2008) reviewed economic methodologies to generate a conceptual framework for classifying existing data on the costs of scaling up HIV/AIDS programs, looking at both short-run and long-run perspectives. She found that there is growing evidence of scale variation among the costs of HIV/AIDS interventions, and that it may explain 26-70 percent of cost variation across locations for similar interventions. Average costs may become larger or smaller as the volume of services expands (as was the case in Brazil’s ARV program between 2001 and 2005), depending on the level of coverage and type of intervention. Key constraints to scaling up include infrastructure investments. She concluded that the available evidence suggests that cost efficiencies associated with scale may reflect different ways of delivering services at higher volumes and also variations in quality. But she concluded that there is a very limited economic evidence base and mechanisms to integrate economic analyses into routine program monitoring are recommended.

Table 2 Evidence from the literature about economies of scale in HIV/AIDS programs

Program	Description	Findings
Vertical transmission	Empirical Cost 15 programs in India	The variation in scale explains 42% of the variation in average cost
VCT	Malawi. Empirical econometric analysis of costs of VCT, data over 34 months	Customers range from 200 to 1600 per month; fixed costs range from 9% to 21% Significant economies of scale estimated rate 1.5. Changes in the production function
VCT	India. VCT 17 empirical cost data, more than 12 months.	334-7802 clients per site per year. Fixed costs average 12.4% of total annual costs. The variation in the cost per customer is assigned 73% to scale
VCT	South Africa. Cost rapid empirical test	662 customers in 1 year, costs decrease by 66% in months

Table 2 Evidence from the literature about economies of scale in HIV/AIDS programs

Program	Description	Findings
Prevention activities in targeted population"	1 Clinical data of 12 months. India. Empirical Cost 15 prevention programs among sex workers, more than 12 months.	of greater burden, suggesting economies of scale Range TS 803-6379. 5.2-8.3% fixed costs (rent, capital). Significant relationship between the scale and size of the program, suggesting economies of scale. Finding of reduced time to be the largest program
Prevention activities in targeted population"	India. Empirical cost of 17 prevention programs in TS. More than one year	Range TS 205-2008. Fixed costs 13-40% (median 15%). 50% of the variation in the average cost attributed to the scale, controlling factors - different production functions Nonparametric analysis shows average cost curve in U, with the minimum average cost occurring in the size of TS 1500 year
Prevention activities in targeted population"	India. Empirical Cost in 15 districts, over 24,000 sex workers in more than 18 months	Fixed costs range from 11 to 32% of the total cost. Sevenfold reduction in the average cost per TS on a scale of activities by district TS 3000. Threefold reduction in average costs for projects started later
Prevention activities in targeted population""	India. Econometric analysis of 78 prevention projects funded by the state and TS 16 projects, more than 12 months	Analysis of expenditure data shows that economies of scale were not exhausted, a fall of 0.002% in the total cost for each person served. The estimation using TS data show an efficiency point on the scale 1.750-2000 people served, approx
Prevention activities in targeted population"	India, Russia and South Africa. Cost empirical TS 40 programs	The scale explains 38-88% of the variation in average costs. Decrease in average costs, not increase
Prevention activities in targeted population"	Russia. Empirical cost of 22 projects to UDI	The scale accounts for 45% of the variation in costs. Turn the scale is associated with a 34.5% reduction in average costs
Treatment of STDs	Thailand. Empirical analysis of incremental costs of STDs	The expansion of evening hours of care in STI clinics 2000 allows processing of additional clients at 31 dol. Everyone
Treatment of STDs	Cambodia. Empirical Cost STDs interventions, a period longer than 3 years	The number of annual visits increased 3 times from 4369 to 13,329 and the cost per visit was reduced to almost half. The decrease is attributed to the large increase in visits
Treatment of STDs	Econometric analysis of average costs of STDs obtained from 53 studies	The scale range is from 3 to 63,693 people a year. The estimates show a small but significant scale effect suggesting that unit costs decrease with scale
Treatment of STDs	India. Empirical cost analysis in 12 districts, reaching more than 20,000 TS, more than 18 months	The average cost per person treated per district was 27 dol. and there was a six fold reduction in average costs by increasing the level of care for patients in more than 1400 patients per district
Treatment of STDs	India, Mexico, Russia	There is a modest effect on the scale with an explanation of 42-70% of costs for the change of the scale. It shows an increase in average costs
VCT, ITS, condom social marketing, IEC	Uganda. Cost empirical randomized over 4 years	Various interventions to 96,000 individuals within communities. An increase of 74% led to a 34% reduction in average cost, suggesting scale effects
IEC	Mexico. Empirical Cost 22 programs	The scale variation explains a proportion of 91%, doubling the scale is a 64% reduction in average costs
Prevention activities in targeted population"	34 sub-Saharan countries. Scale econometric analysis of program costs, to pursue the relationship between the infrastructure of health systems and scale to an increase of 25% coverage	The marginal costs are higher than average cost, suggesting diseconomies of scale. A 25% increase in marginal costs is approximately 7 times higher in care and care for prevention.

According to Kumaranayake (2008), there is evidence of economies (or diseconomies) of scale in HIV/AIDS interventions. Interventions with small proportions of fixed costs such as

VCT and IEC exhibit declining average costs as the scale of activity expands, so it is economically optimal to run larger programs. At the other extreme, interventions related to health benefits (STI or prevention of transmission from mother to child) are likely to face diseconomies of scale and the U-shape of their average cost curves suggests that there is an optimum size for

such programs. The following table summarizes the author's findings regarding the relationship between scale and total or average costs.

3.3. Improvements in efficiency

Stover et al. (2006) find that a strong, global expanded commitment to prevention programs targeted at sexual transmission and transmission among injecting drug users could avert 28 million new worldwide HIV infections between 2005 and 2015. This figure is more than half of the new infections that might otherwise occur during that period in 125 low-and middle-income countries. Although preventing infections, this new investment would require about US\$ 122 billion over this period and would reduce future needs for treatment and care. The analysis suggests that it will cost about US\$ 3,900 to prevent each new infection, but it will produce savings of US\$ 4,700 in forgone treatment costs. Thus, greater spending on prevention not only would prevent more than half the new infections that would occur but from 2005 and 2015, but it would produce a net financial saving as future costs for treatment and care are averted. The figures for the LAC region are as follows: prevention of one case costs US\$ 5,045; present savings and treatment costs averted US\$ 12,330.

Box 1. HIV/AIDS epidemic and response in LAC region

In Latin America and the Caribbean as a whole, the HIV/AIDS epidemic does not have the alarming proportions of sub-Saharan Africa, where the adult prevalence was about 5.2 percent in 2008 (UNAIDS, 2009a). Yet the Caribbean exhibits the second highest level of adult HIV/AIDS prevalence outside of sub-Saharan Africa (about 1.0 percent), and Haiti is the hardest hit country in this region, with an adult prevalence of 2.2 percent of the population. In the LAC region prevalence is not linked with income, as can be seen in Figure 5. Bolivia, which is nearly as poor as Haiti, has a prevalence that is below the regional average and only a fraction of Haiti's. Trinidad & Tobago, the richest country in LAC, has the third highest prevalence. In LAC there is a slightly negative relationship between national income and total spending on HIV/AIDS (including public and private domestic and international resources; Figure 7). The Dominican Republic and Ecuador, two of the three countries selected for this study, exhibit lower total spending than would be expected given their income, whereas Guatemala spends about what one would predict given its income. In addition, in LAC the combined spending on HIV/AIDS, expressed as a proportion of national income, increases with prevalence, implying that the countries with a more severe epidemic devote a greater share of own and international resources to fight it (Figure 8 and Figure 9).

Figure 5 Prevalence of HIV/AIDS, % population 15-49b

Figure 6 Total HIV/AIDS spending as % of GNI

Figure 7 Total HIV/AIDS spending as % of GNI, excluding Haiti

Figure 8 Prevalence of HIV/AIDS, % population 15-49

Figure 9 Prevalence of HIV/AIDS, % population 15-49, excluding Haiti

4. Current situation in Ecuador

4.1. Demographic and epidemiologic data

The first case of AIDS in Ecuador was reported in 1984. Since then the Ministry of Public Health (MOH) made the reporting of HIV/AIDS cases mandatory by law, nonetheless many cases are never officially reported due to fear or distrust that the information will not be treated confidentially. The current situation of the country, including the epidemic, spending, and a comparison of the current situation with countries in the region is presented in this section.

According to data for the years 2008-2009, the epidemiological situation was as follows:

- *Population:* According to the World Bank the total population in Ecuador was 13.48 million in 2008. The World Bank projections estimate that the population will reach 15.5 million people by 2023, with a total growth of 15 percent in the period.
- *HIV/AIDS Population:* According to UNAIDS the number of reported cases in the country are approximately 26,000. Adult prevalence was 0.3 percent. The reported number of deaths per year due to AIDS was 1,200 people that translate into a case fatality rate of 4.61 percent.
- *HIV/AIDS Case fatality rate:* According to UNAIDS was 4.6% in 2008.

In Ecuador, the epidemic is in a concentrated phase with a tendency towards growth, maintaining a prevalence of less than 0.3 percent. Sexual intercourse is the most common way of transmission accounting for 96.9 percent of all notified cases, this directly relates to the scarce use of condoms which is around a meager 1.5 percent, as well as an increase of STDs. Around 2.6 percent of the cases are related to mother to child transmission and just 0.2 percent of the cases are due to use of intravenous drug use. Currently there are no reported cases of HIV/AIDS transmission due to blood transfusions.

Figure 10 presents the trend of the epidemic measured by reported cases demonstrating a progressive increase. This is not only due to more people acquiring HIV/AIDS but also because of the improvement in reporting, mostly because of the expansion of voluntary counseling and testing (VCT) and a better information system. From 2006 onwards this improvement is evident.

Figure 10 Annual increase of reported HIV/AIDS cases and related deaths, 1984-2009

Source: MOH-PNS (National Program of HIV/AIDS). Ecuador 2009

The HIV/AIDS case reporting showed that the higher number of cases reported belong to Guayas where the majority of PLWHA also reside.

Another important issue to illustrate the epidemic distribution is gender. In Ecuador men have more reported HIV and AIDS cases than women, for example: in 2009 the male AIDS cases were 919 (71%), whereas female cases totaled 376 (29%) of the total cases reported that year.

Figure 11 shows the gender epidemic distribution of HIV and AIDS cases from 1984 to 2008, the total population, and the prevalence rate for each year. It is evident that the difference in number of cases and prevalence rate between men and women has diminished progressively with a trend to leveling out (2:1; male:female).

The main causes of death for patients with the HIV virus are infectious and parasitic diseases, especially the co-infection HIV-TB which represents 38 percent of the total deaths.

Figure 11 Deaths resulting from HIV/AIDS

4.2. Facing the epidemic

In Ecuador, the Ministry of Public Health (MOH) is the main stakeholder leading the national response against the HIV/AIDS epidemic. It is through this institution that most of the spending and investment is done, channeling private and international funding and primarily directing investment towards the areas of treatment and prevention. Over time there are several factors that have improved HIV/AIDS treatment and prevention. For instance, the commitment of the government in funding the response to the HIV/AIDS epidemic has grown demonstrating the increasing spending in care and treatment by the MOH that accounts for about 86 percent, whereas in prevention accounts for almost 44 percent of total expenditure. Indeed, the MOH expenditure in all categories represents almost three quarters of the total HIV/AIDS expenditure. In addition, the MOH is responsible for policy development and enforcement through the National Program for Prevention and Control of HIV/AIDS.

4.3. Economic and financing data

- *Per capita income*: Ecuador has a per capita income of 8,008 (PPP, international dollars).
- *Health expenditure as GDP%*: Ecuador spends a 5,8% of its GDP in health, equivalent to 297 (PPP, international dollars) per capita. The public expenditure is a 39,1% of the total expenditure in health (THE).
- *Expenditure on HIV/AIDS during 2005-2007*: The National AIDS Spending Assessment (NASA) Report showed a total HIV/AIDS spending of about US\$ 20.58 million, of which 45 percent was from public sources, 54 percent from international sources, and a mere 1 percent from private local sources (see
- *Per capita AIDS health expenditure/PLWHA*: Ecuador spends 287 (PPP, international dollars) per year in every person that has HIV or AIDS. The amount is similar to per capita health expenditure. Is not there a difference between PLWHA and an average citizen
- *Per capita AIDS health expenditure/total population*: 0,56 dollars, equivalent to a 0,2% of total expenditure in health.
- *Per capita AIDS health expenditure/PLWHA*: Ecuador spends 287 (PPP, international dollars) per year in every person that has HIV or AIDS. The amount is similar to per capita health expenditure. Is not there a difference between PLWHA and an average citizen

The per capita expenditure on HIV/AIDS is presented in Table 3 comparing the spending on 2007 versus the period 2008-2009. The calculations were made based on the estimated total population for 2008 and the total population living with HIV/AIDS. The per capita expenditure has increased almost threefold in the last two years. The expenditure on HIV/AIDS as a percentage of the GDP has also grown from 0.0009 percent in 2007 to 0.0012 percent in 2008-2009.

Government spending in health has also increased in the last three years shows the MOH budget by category of spending for the period 2006-2009 and calculates the share of the GDP.

Table 3 Per capita HIV/AIDS expenditure

Year	Total HIV/AIDS Expenditure (US\$)	GDP (%)	MOH budget (%)	Per capita global population (US\$)	Per capita PLWHA (US\$)
2007	20,588,493	0.0009	3.3	1.51	791.87
2008-2009	58,044,279	0.0012	3.7	4.26	2,232.47

Source: INEC 2010; MOH-PNS (National Program of HIV/AIDS). Ecuador 2009

The expenditure on HIV/AIDS shows a growing trend. It becomes more important on years 2007 and 2008 because grows on a 130 percent. In 2009 the total spending increased on 30 percent over last year, how is show in Figure 12.

Figure 12 Total expenditure on HIV/AIDS by year, 2005-2009 (US\$)

Source: NASA Ecuador.

This increase was mainly a result of a bigger flow of international funds, particularly during 2006 where the Global Fund spending was almost four times greater than in 2005 from 1.51 million to 5.71 million, respectively. During 2007 international funding was still an important source of financing accounting for 56 percent of all funding representing an expenditure of 4.33 million.

The structure of HIV/AIDS financing changed profoundly during the period 2008– 2009. In this regard, international funding had relatively decreased due to a significant increase in government spending mainly through resources allocated to the MOH, as a result of the government public policy geared towards strengthening the social sector public services. Therefore, the funding for HIV/AIDS took a quantum leap from 20.58 million for the period 2005-2007 to 58 million for 2008-2009, representing an increase of 281 percent, mostly because of the higher public spending, illustrates this change in the HIV/AIDS financing, and Figure 13 represents the respective proportions per year. In sum, it is evident that government spending, currently, is the main source of financing accounting for around 80 percent of the total expenditure. In absolute terms, public funds increased ten times between years 2005 and 2009; reaching the 82% of the total spending on HIV/AIDS in 2009, how its show in Figure 13.

The above mentioned growth in the HIV/AIDS spending is not only the result of more government resources being allocated, but also a significant improvement in the accounting methods and information gathering. The NASA carried out for 2005-2007 only collected information from 17 institutions while the 2008-2009 version collected information from 49

different sources. In addition, the latter also improved the methodology to prevent double accounting and to take into account only data from actual spending, disregarding programmed spending. Private funds are almost negligible in this analysis.

Figure 13 HIV/AIDS sources of financing, 2005-2009 (percentage)

Source: NASA Ecuador 2005-2009

4.4. Uses of resources

The total expenditure on HIV/AIDS is classified according to a category of expenditure, dominated last years: prevention (40%) and treatment and care with 35% (see Figure 14)

Figure 14: HIV/AIDS expenditure by categories, 2005-2009 (percentage)

Source: NASA Ecuador 2005-2009

Table 4 summarizes the expenditure by spending category and source of financing for the period 2005- 2007:

Table 4 Sources of HIV/AIDS financing and categories of spending, 2007 (percentage)

Spending category	Sources of financing			Total
	Public	Private	External	
Prevention	46.2	0	53.8	26.6
Care and treatment	98.5	0.1	1.4	31.3
Orphans and vulnerable children	0	0	0	0
Program management	1.6	0.6	97.7	22.6
Human resources	0	0.7	99.3	5.5
Favorable environment	0	0.8	99.2	1.4
HIV/AIDS research	0	0	100	12.5
Total	43.5	0.2	56.2	100

Source: NASA Ecuador 2007

The expenditure according to the various spending categories and sources of financing was as follows in 2007:

Public funding was clearly directed almost exclusively towards prevention and treatment.

External Funds assumes almost the all expenditure of program administration, training, investigation in HIV/AIDS and prevention.

Private financing which amounts to very little actual spending also went primarily towards program management, although not being a significant share in the overall expenditure.

Lately, the spending structure for the period 2008-2009 demonstrates that the majority of resources went to treatment and prevention, representing 51 million out of the total 58 million spent. Again government spending through the MOH accounts for nearly 85 percent in prevention and 98 percent in treatment. Other relevant spending areas were human resources and program management, but only represented a combined result of about 8 percent.

Table 5 Expenditure in care and treatment services 2008 and 2009 (US\$)

Spending category	2008	2009	Total
HIV care and treatment (4 medical consultations, laboratory tests VL and CD4 , and ARV treatment per patient per year)	3,459,957	4,324,018	7,783,975
Care and prophylaxis excluding ARVs	3,148,674	2,555,262	5,703,936
HIV care (2 medical consultations, laboratory tests VL and CD4 per patient per year)	1,600,365	2,034,442	3,634,807
Provision of services	389	524	91
HIV/AIDS hospitalization cost	289	361	651
ARV for patients with TB	4	45	86
Total care and treatment (MOH)	-	-	18,771,273
Total including prevention category	-	-	42,118,420

Source: NASA Ecuador 2008-2009

Amongst the improvements in the last years is worth noting the case notification system. In fact, investment efforts geared towards improving accuracy, timeliness and easiness of reporting resulted in better information.

Other effort has been, implementing changes in VCT to make counseling and testing widely available throughout the country, alongside greater privacy and easier testing methods have increased the number of reported HIV/AIDS cases. As can be seen in Table 5, the number of cases reported during 2008 and 2009 represent approximately 40 percent of all notified cases since the onset of the epidemic.

The expansion of antiretroviral coverage is also related to the sustained increase of government spending in HIV/AIDS which started in 2004 (see Figure 15). The aim of the MOH is give access to antiretroviral therapy to all the people living with HIV/AIDS as stated in the guidelines for comprehensive care for PLWHA that was first drafted in 2004 and the last review was published in 2009. The MOH has 28 HIV/AIDS well equipped clinics nationwide to provide prevention, diagnosis and treatment in a decentralized scheme. In addition, there are around 250 primary care health centers which provide VCT services.

Figure 15 Ecuador: estimated antiretroviral coverage 2004-2007 (percentage)

Source: UNAIDS (http://cfs.unaids.org/country_factsheet.aspx?ISO=ECU)

Ecuador has also aligned its national response to HIV/AIDS with the Millennium Development Goals through the Multisectorial Strategic Plan for 2007-2015 (PEM) that identified ten priority sectors. According to the 2008-2009 UNGASS report, the plan has been implemented partially remaining several gaps to fulfill if Ecuador is to achieve the 2015 goals. Since September 2009 the plan is under revision to fine tune activities according to the new priorities arising from the concentrated epidemics definition that was adopted in late 2008. One of the weaknesses on implementation was the absence of annual operating plans by sector that precluded clear and concrete actions. Furthermore, it also lacks a monitoring and evaluation process to identify advancement on objectives completion and provide timely information to correct problems, change strategy and fortify interventions.

An important effort has been made by the NAP developing a prioritization tool to focus intervention in the areas of the country that are in most need by combining several indicators such as greatest incidence of poverty, HIV/AIDS and tuberculosis.

4.5. Stakeholders

MOH

In Ecuador, the Ministry of Public Health (MOH) is the main stakeholder leading the national response against the HIV/AIDS epidemic.

International Organizations

Among the main foreign stakeholders that contribute to the national response against HIV/AIDS are United Nations Organizations like UNAIDS, UNDP, UNFPA and PAHO. In addition, CARE which has received funds from the European Union to implement a project on HIV/AIDS fostering the participation of local governments and the private sector in the response to the HIV/AIDS epidemic. International organizations have contributed a total of \$US\$ 3.8 million for the years 2008 and 2009 which is a relatively small amount compared to the investment made by the government. The following table shows how much international organizations invested in the HIV/AIDS response.

It is evident that the spending priority for international organizations is prevention accounting for 40.4 percent of the total resources spent in the period 2008 – 2009. Program administration represents the next spending category for international organizations with 21 percent for the same period.

Table 6 Investment by international organizations, 2008 and 2009 (US\$)

International organization	2008	2009	Total	%
CARE (financed by the EU)	816,339	825,122	1,641,461	42
UNFPA	258,905	282,126	541,031	14
UNDP	311,729	229,191	54,092	12
PAHO	204,379	25,855	462,929	1
UNICEF	N/A	45	45	0
UNAIDS	176,667	186,243	36,291	9
GTZ	N/A	79,796	79,796	4
UNESCO	57,967	N/A	57,967	0
UNIFEM	N/A	36,374	36,374	2
WFP	N/A	3,771	3,771	0
Others	0	311,589	892,341	16
Total	1,825,986	1,980,112	3,806,098	100

Source: NASA Ecuador 2008-2009

Table 7 Total expenditure in Prevention by International organizations per year (US\$)

International organization	2008	2009	TOTAL
CARE (Financed by the EU)	282,498	344,456	626,954
UNFPA	143,568	197,944	341,512
PNUD	130,171	97,818	227,989
GTZ	N/A	79,796	79,796
UNIFEM	N/A	31,374	31,374
PAHO	64,297	8,475	149,047
UNICEF	N/A	34	34
UNESCO	42,704	N/A	42,704
UNAIDS	5,063	N/A	5,063
TOTAL	668,301	870,138	1,538,439

Source: NASA Ecuador 2008-2009

Private and Civil Society organizations investing on the HIV/AIDS response

The contribution of private and civil society organizations towards the expenditure on the HIV/AIDS response is marginal, barely getting to 9.37 percent of the total spending in all areas. “Equidad foundation” is the most relevant spending contributor with 46.7 percent of the total spending, however it is due to funding received to implement a two year research project on HIV/AIDS prevalence and risk behavior among MSM. The following table demonstrates spending by 8 selected private and civil society institutions.

Table 8 Private and civil society spending by organization (US\$).

Private and Civil Society organizations	2008	2009	TOTAL
Equidad Foundation	87,303	1,196,609	2,069,639

Red Cross	441,919	363,896	805,815
Junta de Beneficencia de Guayaquil	145,701	215,197	360,898
VIHDA Foundation	44,642	154,913	199,555
REDIMA	105,921	99,254	205,175
MAP International	66,075	53,759	119,834
KIMIRINA	141,898	33,277	474,668
Asociación ALFIL	nd	12,994	12,994
TOTAL	1,819,186	2,429,392	4,248,578

Source: NASA Ecuador 2008-2009

Table 9 shows the average yearly out of pocket expenditure of families on health care in Ecuador revealing that main spending items are hospitalization and health insurance. The expenditure in condoms is very low compared to the other categories. There is no data available to assess private expenditure on HIV/AIDS, but as a proxy Table 10 presents the annual public expenditure on HIV/AIDS treatment by ARV scheme for 2010.

Table 9 Average expenditure on health care by category 2005 (US\$)

Spending category	Mean	Standard Deviation	Low Range	High Range
Hospitalization	370.3	746.3	376	1,116.6
Other health expenditures	204	557.3	353.3	761.3
Health insurance	143.2	858.8	715.6	1,002
Drugs	53.3	144.1	90.8	197.3
Ambulance services	33.5	39.3	5.9	72.8
Clinical laboratory tests	28	182	153.9	210
Professional medical care	25	129.1	104.1	154.1
Non professional medical care	19.2	94.8	75.6	114
Condoms	3.2	2.8	0.5	6

Source: INEC Household Survey 2005.

Table 10 Public expenditure on HIV/AIDS treatment 2010 (US\$)

Treatment scheme	ARV	Condoms	Consults	CD4	CV	Indirect Costs	Total Annual Cost
ABC+DDI+ATV+RTV	634,231	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	662,787
DDI+ABC+SQV+RTV	401,848	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	430,403
3TC+DDI+SQV+RTV	352,451	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	381,007
D4T+3TC+SQV+RTV	317,168	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	345,723
AZT+3TC+SQV+RTV	288,576	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	317,132
3TC+SQV+LPV/R	267,168	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	295,723
ABC+3TC+EFV+SQV+RTV*	247,470	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	276,026
D4T+DDI+IDV	242,117	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	270,672
ABC+DDI (400)+LPV/R	228,965	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	257,520
DDI+ABC+LPV/R	228,965	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	257,520
D4T+DDI+LPV/R	196,115	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	224,670
ABC+D4T+LPV/R	193,681	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	222,237
3TC+DDI+LPV/R	179,568	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	208,123
ABC+3TC+LPV/R	177,135	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	205,690
AZT+DDI+LPV/R	175,918	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	204,473
AZT+ABC+LPV/R	173,485	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	202,040
AZT+3TC+IDV	161,695	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	190,251
DDI+ABC+EFV	146,000	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	174,556
TDF+FTC+EFV	146,000	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	174,556
D4T+3TC+LPV/R	144,285	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	172,840
AZT+3TC+EFV+LPV/r	132,726	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	161,282
RTV	119,581	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	148,137
LPV/R+EFV	117,031	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	145,587
AZT+3TC+LPV/R	115,693	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	144,248
D4T+DDI+EFV	113,150	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	141,706
DDI+3TC+NVP	107,310	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	135,866
3TC+DDI+EFV	96,603	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	125,159
ABC+3TC+EFV	9,417	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	122,726
AZT+DDI+EFV	92,953	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	121,509
AZT+ABC+EFV	9,052	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	119,076
AZT+3TC+D4T+EFV	63,145	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	91,701
TDF+FTC	62,914	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	91,469
D4T (30)+3TC+EFV	6,132	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	89,876
D4T (30)+3TC+NVP	48,667	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	77,222
D4T+3TC	44,287	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	72,842
AZT+3TC+NVP	43,435	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	71,991
TDF + ZDV + 3TC/FTC	41,975	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	70,531
AZT+3TC+NVP (FDC)	365	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	65,056
AZT+3TC+EFV (FDC)	32,728	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	61,284
AZT+3TC+NfV	15,695	75	1,125	5,333	7,622	36	44,251

Source: Authors

5. Methods

This section describes the model built to project spending and financing of HIV/AIDS interventions in Ecuador, the model's assumptions and the data sources.

5.1. Model description

This section begins with an overview of the logic of the HIV/AIDS financing gap model, followed by a description of the methods used to forecast the epidemic. Next it explains how the associated prevention and treatment costs were drawn in the model, and then presents the assumptions made to predict financing. Finally, it shows how financing gaps are estimated.

Overview: The main idea in this HIV/AIDS gap projection model is as follows: The model separately projects the demand for resources for HIV/AIDS interventions, including

promotive, preventive, and curative activities, and the supply of resources coming from government, households, and donors (see Figure 16). The demand for resources is the projected costs of HIV/AIDS interventions. The supply of resources is the projected financing. A comparison of demand and supply, for each year of the projected horizon, indicates whether there is a gap in financing (demand > supply) or sufficient financing (demand = supply), or a surplus in financing (demand ≤ supply). If there is a projected gap (as illustrated in Figure 17) simulations can be carried out through the model to examine whether changes in targets or strategies can lower the demand for financing. Examples of changes in strategy would be an increase in program efficiency through measures such as the centralized purchasing of ARVs, or an increase the supply of financing, for example through the use of new sources of financing.

Figure 16 Alternative hypothetical scenarios regarding the projected sufficiency of financing for HIV/AIDS at country level

The authors made annual projections for the period 2009-2023 of both required resources (demand) for HIV/AIDS and allocated resources (supply). They formulated 3 scenarios each for demand and supply (base, optimistic, and pessimistic, all 6 described below in greater detail), giving rise to 9 combined scenarios. For each of these 9 scenarios the authors computed on an annual basis the expected financing gap (if any, if not the surplus) over the projected horizon 2009-2023. Projections of demand and supply are presented in an itemized fashion according to the categories defined in the country's NASA.

Figure 17 Hypothetical scenario where an increase in program efficiency is used to breach the projected financing gap

Epidemic: The trend of the epidemic was drawn through the year 2015 using official estimates made by national authorities. Beyond 2015 the authors adopted a phased approach based on the following six parameters that characterize the epidemic:

- Current and projected total population
- Reported cases
- Estimated cases
- Prevalence of reported cases
- Underreporting
- Case fatality rate

The year 2008 was defined as the base year. Although NASA results are available both for 2008 and 2009, the authors decided to use 2008 as the base year in this study to allow comparability with the two other study countries for which the most recent NASA data available are for 2008.

In 2008 the total population in the country was 13.8 million, the number of reported HIV/AIDS cases was 10,765, and the total estimated population living with HIV/AIDS was 37,132 people, for a rate of underreporting of 71 percent. The national prevalence was 0.3 percent. The model assumes a gradual reduction in underreporting to reflect a successful effort by the national HIV/AIDS authority to expand coverage.

Whereas Ecuadorian health authorities have their own, official projection of the course of the epidemic, these authors found it necessary to consider alternative scenarios for the epidemic to come up with an internally consistent model. Figure 19 compares the officially projected path of the epidemic (upper curve) with a projection made by the authors fitting a polynomial equation to the historic data for the period 2000-2008. As can be seen, the official projection lies well above the statistical projection. It is unlikely that despite an ever growing response to the epidemic the incidence will grow at an increasing rate, as in the official projection. Since the authors of this report were unable to ascertain the basis for the official figures they decided to make their own base projection, represented by the lower curve, and use it in their various scenarios.

Figure 18 Impact of alternative HIV/AIDS control strategies on prevalence: an illustrative hypothetical example

Figure 19 PLWHA: historic data (2000-2008) and projections (2009-2023)

The need to model the future number of cases instead of using a static projection also obeys to the need to make the future incidence of HIV/AIDS endogenous to the model’s parameters. For example, as is illustrated in Figure 18, the future course of the epidemic will vary relative to a baseline scenario if Ecuador adopts a more aggressive and therefore more effective strategy to treat PLWHA with ARVs, for example changing the CD4 count that triggers ARV treatment from 100 to 350. Such a change has two different and opposing consequences. First, it reduces incidence and this effect results in a drop in the number of PLWHA. Second, it reduces mortality among PLWHA, an effect that results in an increase in the number of PLWHA. The resulting net effect on the number of PLWHA will depend on the relative magnitude of these two effects. While the authors did not find empirical information from the literature regarding the effect of a change in the CD4 count policy on incidence, they did find a study indicating that when the coverage of ARV therapies increases from 50 percent to 75 percent and remains at this higher level over a 30-year period, incidence drops by 26 percent.² This would reduce the number of new cases and therefore the total projected number of PLWHA. They also found that when the CD4 count is changed from 100 to 350, mortality among PLWHA drops by 6 percent each year.³ Then they combined these two opposing effect to project the number of PLWHA through 2023 in Ecuador.

5.2. Projections of demand for and supply of HIV/AIDS resources

In accordance with Ecuador’s NASA methodology, the model uses the following 8 spending categories.

- Prevention

² Johnston KM et al. Expanding access to HAART: a cost-effective approach for treating and preventing HIV. AIDS, advance online publication: DOI:10. 1097/QAD.0bo13e32833af85d, 2010.

³ (a) Life expectancy of individuals on combination antiretroviral therapy in high-income countries: a collaborative analysis of 14 cohort studies. The Antiretroviral Therapy Cohort Collaboration. The Lancet - 26 July 2008 (Vol. 372, Issue 9635, Pages 293 - 299). DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(08)61113-7 and (b) ARV treatment cuts mortality rate in early and late treaters. AIDS MEDS, January 5, 2010.

- Care and treatment
- Orphans and vulnerable children
- Program management
- Human resources
- Social protection and social services
- Favorable environment
- HIV/AIDS research

To project costs the model considers that some costs vary according to projected activities (for example, ARV treatment costs, or the distribution of condoms, or the ambulatory or inpatient treatment of PLWHA) while some other costs are not associated to any specific coverage targets.

Target-related interventions. Ecuador aims at universal coverage of all PLWHA by 2015. Table 11 presents each intervention, its population coverage in 2008, and its projected coverage by the year 2015. It also shows the cost share of each intervention, where 100 percent is Ecuador's total national spending on HIV/AIDS. The coverage rates achieved in 2015 are projected to remain constant through 2023. Current coverage rates were obtained from the most recent UNGASS report (2008-2009).

Table 11 Cost components for target-related interventions, cost share, current coverage (2008) and coverage targets (2015) (percent)

Spending category	Spending item	Spending share 2008	Coverage 2008	Coverage target 2015
Prevention	Communication for social change and behavioral health	3.7	69.2	100.0
	Counseling and voluntary testing	2.6	87.0	100.0
	Social marketing of condoms	0.2	14.0	80.0
	Prevention - Youth outside the educational system	1.8	3.0	15.0
	Prevention - youth attending educational institutions.	0.5	63.0	100.0
	Prevention of transmission mother son	0.1	85.0	100.0
	Prevention, diagnosis and treatment of sexually transmitted infections	0.4	37.0	50.0
	Programs for men who have sex with men	2.8	78.2	80.0
	Programs for sex workers and their clients	1.6	97.0	100.0
	Supplies of condoms for men in public and commercial sector	0.3	47.0	100.0
Treatment and care	Outpatient	9.6	55.3	100.0
	First-line antiretroviral therapy	4.0	55.3	100.0
	Second-line antiretroviral therapy	3.6	55.3	100.0
	Therapy antiretroviral after the failure of second-line treatment	0.0	55.3	100.0
	Therapy antiretroviral adults not disaggregated treatment line	0.0	55.3	100.0
	Treatment of opportunistic infections	26.7	55.3	100.0
Total		58.1		

Source: NASA Ecuador 2008 - UNGASS 2010.

Once universal coverage is reached in 2015, the costs associated to the epidemic are modeled in proportion to either the total population growth or the growth in the PLWHA, as is shown in Table 12.

Table 12 Variables intervening in the determination of costs for target-related interventions, 2015-2023

Costs categories	Function – Details of Cost categories	PLWHA growth rate	Total population growth rate
Prevention	Communication for social and behavioral change		X
	Voluntary testing and counseling (VTC)		X
	Prevention – young at school		X
	Prevention-young not at school		X
	Prevention program for sex workers and clients		X
	Prevention program for men having sex with men		X
	Condom social commercialization		X
	Male condom supply in commercial and public sector		X
	Prevention and treatment of ITS		X
	Prevention of Mother-to-Child Transmission (PMTCT)	X	
Care and treatment	Ambulatory care	X	
	Hospital care	X	
	Care services and treatment not itemized by intervention	X	

X indicates that the variable was used to determine the cost of the intervention.

Source: NASA Ecuador 2008 - UNGASS 2010.

No target interventions. Costs with no associated targets were calculated preserving their cost share of 2008, when they represented 41.9 percent of total HIV-AIDS costs in the country. The procedure to project these costs was as follows: first the model used actual spending information from 2008 to compute total target-related costs. Second, it assumed that these costs represented a constant 58.1 percent of total costs, as in 2008. Third, is computed the total spending amount dividing spending on the target-related costs by 58.1 percent. Fourth, to compute the cost of each spending item not linked to a target, it applied the cost share of that item in 2008 and shown in Table 13.

Table 13 Cost components and cost share for interventions not linked with coverage targets (2015) (%)

Spending category	Spending item	Spending share 2008 (%)	Projected annual growth through 2015
Program management	Management and transaction costs associated with management of funds	0.0	8.7
	Strengthening of the Administration and management of programs not unbundled by intervention	3.5	8.7
	Operations research	0.1	8.7
	Improvement and construction of infrastructure	0.0	8.7
	Monitoring and evaluation	0.0	0.0
	Planning, coordination and management of the program	3.9	8.7
	Medicines stock system	0.0	8.7
	Staff monitoring and follow-up of patients	0.0	0.0
	Information technology	0.0	0.0
	Mandatory HIV (not VCT) test	0.1	8.7
	HIV drug resistance surveillance	0.0	0.0
Sero-surveillance	0.4	8.7	
Enabling environment	Defense and strategic communication	0.5	8.7
	Community development and enhanced to reduce vulnerability not disaggregated by intervention environment	0.5	8.7
	Institutional development specifically linked to AIDS	0.4	8.7
	Human rights program	0.2	8.7
	Specific programs on AIDS for women	0.0	0.0
Orphans and vulnerable children	Programs to reduce violence based on gender	0.1	8.7
	Community support	0.0	0.0
	Support for family / home to orphans and vulnerable children	0.1	8.7
	Institutional care	0.0	0.0
	Basic medical care for orphans and vulnerable children [9]	0.0	0.0
Education for orphans and vulnerable children	0.2	8.7	

Table 13 Cost components and cost share for interventions not linked with coverage targets (2015) (%)

Spending category	Spending item	Spending share 2008 (%)	Projected annual growth through 2015
	Universal precautions	0.0	0.0
	OVC does not disaggregated intervention services	0.0	0.0
	Social services and administrative costs	0.0	0.0
HIV Research	Biomedical research	0.0	0.0
	Social Sciences Research	0.0	0.0
	Clinical research	0.0	0.0
	Epidemiological research	0.1	8.7
	Research related to HIV not disaggregated intervention	0.5	8.7
	Research related to vaccines	0.2	8.7
	Prevention	Not disaggregated intervention prevention activities	20.9
Male circumcision		0.0	0.0
Injections medical safe		0.0	0.0
Safe medical injections		0.0	0.0
Microbicides		0.0	0.0
Community mobilization		1.2	8.7
Universal precautions		1.5	8.7
HIV transmission prevention for people living with HIV		1.7	8.7
Post-exposure prophylaxis		0.0	0.0
Prevention programs in the workplace		0.1	8.7
Programs for the reduction of damage by injections of people who use drugs		0.0	0.0
Provision of condoms for women in public and commercial sector		0.0	0.0
Reducing risk to vulnerable populations and accessible		0.4	8.7
Safe blood		0.0	0.0
Social protection and social service		Specific income generation	0.0
	Social protection through monetary benefits	0.5	8.7
	Social protection through the provision of social services	0.0	0.0
	Welfare benefits in kind	0.0	0.0
	Social protection and social service not disaggregated by intervention	0.0	0.0
Human resources	Formative education to build a workforce	0.3	8.7
	Training	0.5	8.7
	Monetary incentives for HR	1.8	8.7
	HR not disaggregated intervention	0.0	8.7
Treatment	Other services of care and treatment not disaggregated intervention	0.0	0.0
	Not disaggregated care in hospital services	2.2	8.7
	Emergency rescue and transport of patients	0.0	0.0
Total		41.9	

Beyond 2015 costs not related to coverage targets were modeled in proportion to either the total population growth or the growth in the PLWHA, as is shown in Table 12 costs not linked to targets were modeled in proportion The same criterion used in the categories and coverage targets is applied from 2016 onwards. In the case of interventions for PLWHA the epidemic growth rate was applied, whilst for the other interventions the total population growth rate was used. The parameter employed in every cost category is illustrated in Table 14.

Table 14 Variables intervening in the determination of costs for interventions not related to target, 2015-2023

Spending category	Cost item	PLWHA growth rate	Total population growth rate
Prevention	Community mobilization		X
	Risk reduction for vulnerable and accessible population	X	
	Preventing HIV transmission targeting people living with HIV/AIDS (PLWHA)	X	
	Prevention programs in the workplace		X
	Prevention activities not itemized by interventions		X

Table 14 Variables intervening in the determination of costs for interventions not related to target, 2015-2023

Spending category	Cost item	PLWHA growth rate	Total population growth rate
	Prevention activities s.c.o.		X
Orphans and vulnerable children	Education for HIV		X
	Family support		X
Program management	Plan, coordination and management programs		X
	Administration and transaction costs related to the management and payment of funds		X
	Surveillance and evaluation		X
	Operational research		X
	Drugs supply systems		X
	Infrastructure upgrade and construction		X
	Mandatory HIV tests		X
	Management and administration programs not itemized by type		X
	Management and administration of s.c.o programs		X
Human resources	Monetary incentives for human resources		X
	HIV task force training courses		X
	Capacity building		X
	Human resources not itemized by type		X
	Income generating projects for HIV		X
Enabling environment	Mass advocacy		X
	Advocacy human rights program		X
	AIDS specific institutional development		X
	Favorable environment not itemized by type		X
	Favorable environment s.c.o.		X
HIV Research	Research activities related to HIV not itemized by type		X
	Research activities related to HIV s.c.o		X
	Epidemiology research		X

X indicates that the variable was used to determine the cost of the intervention.

Source: NASA Ecuador 2008-Consultants

Projection scenarios: the following table describes the 3 demand and 3 supply scenarios projected in the model. The Base Scenario most closely resembles the current circumstances and reflects existing information about future costs and funding commitments by government and donors. It also assumes that the country will be able to reach its coverage targets by 2015 and that these targets will remain constant afterwards.

On the demand side, the Efficiency Scenario assumes that there are cost savings resulting from both economies of scale in the purchasing of ARVs and improved management (see Box 1). The Lower Coverage Scenario assumes that universal coverage is not reached until 2023, instead of 2015 (in the Base and Efficiency scenarios). Hence, the relationship between the magnitudes of the resources demanded in the three scenarios is as follows:

Base Scenario > Efficiency Scenario > Lower Coverage Scenario

On the supply side the Optimistic Scenario assumes that both government and donors increase their funding relative to the Base Scenario while household spending grows in tandem with GNI. The Pessimistic Scenario assumes that future funding from government and households will be smaller than in the two preceding scenarios while funding from donors will drop to zero after 2015. Thus, the relationship between the magnitudes of the resources supplied in the three scenarios is as follows:

Optimistic Scenario > Base Scenario > Pessimistic Scenario

From the above formulation of scenarios, it follows that the combination of scenarios that will produce the biggest gap in funding will be the Base Demand Scenario combined with the Pessimistic Supply Scenario. Conversely, the combination that will yield the smallest gap will be the Lower Coverage Demand Scenario combined with the Optimistic Supply Scenario.

Box 1: Management costs of HIV/AIDS programs in the LAC region

In 2008, management costs were below 7 percent for all countries in the region, with the exception of Guatemala, where they represented 15 percent, and the Dominican Republic, where they accounted for more than one-fourth of all HIV/AIDS resources. In Ecuador, management costs were 5 percent of total HIV/AIDS spending, in line with most countries in the region. Still, there were countries in the region, such as Cuba, Costa Rica, Colombia, and Panama, that managed to devote as little as 1 percent of their costs to management. It is important to understand why Guatemala and the Dominican Republic had such a high management burden and to unveil the mechanisms that may enable those two countries to improve program efficiency by reducing their management spending.

Figure 20 Expenditure comparisons between Ecuador and Latin America and the Caribbean countries, circa 2008

Source: Authors from UNAIDS 2010 (www.unaids.org) and World Bank 2010 (www.worldbank.org).

Figure 21 Demand and supply scenarios

Demand scenarios		Supply scenarios		
D1 (Base)	Reach universal coverage for all interventions by 2015 and maintain this coverage through 2023	S1 (Base)	Public sources	Remains constant as a percentage of GNI through 2023
			Households	Annual out-of-pocket spending by households is projected such that average spending per PLWHA remains constant and equal to its observed 2008 value
			Donors	Current funding commitments by donors are kept through 2015 then this funding category drops in a linear fashion to become 0 in the year 2023
D2 (Efficiency)	Same coverage assumptions as in D1 but in addition there is a projected reduction in costs from efficiency measures in management and ARV costs	S2 (Optimistic)	Public sources	Remains constant as a percentage of GNI through 2015, then grows progressively to double in percentage in 2023
			Households	Household out-of-pocket spending grows at the same rate as the GNI
			Donors	They preserve they current funding unaltered in absolute, real terms through 2023
D3 (Lower Coverage)	Reach universal coverage by 2023 and no cost-efficiency measures	S3 (Pessimistic)	Public sources	Future GNI growth, beyond 2008, is supposed to be the lowest growth observed in the preceding three years, 2006-2008
			Households	Annual out-of-pocket spending by households is projected such that average spending per PLWHA remains constant and equal to its lowest observed value in the period 2006-2008
			Donors	Beyond 2015 donor funding drops to 0

5.3. Gap calculation

In any given year there is projected financing gap if demand and supply of resources differ. If demand is greater than supply, there is a deficit in financing and new sources of funding or measures to reduce costs are required; if supply is greater than demand there is a financing surplus, in which case one or more funding levels can be reduced or interventions can be expanded. The full gap projection model is shown below in Figure 23.

Figure 22 Demand, supply and gap scenarios

Figure 23 Projection model for establishing future financing gaps

6. Sources of information

This study used multiple sources of information for demography, epidemiology, economic growth, costs, funding, etc. The sources include Ecuador’s National Institute of Statistics (INEC), and the Central Bank, the OECD Health Data, the Ministry of Health’s MOH, HIV/AIDS program, the NASA reports for 2005-2007 and 2008-2009, the UNGASS report 2008-2009, and information provided by experts. The exact data source used is shown as a note under each table and figure in this report.

7. Results

7.1. Evolution of the epidemic

In its base scenario the model projects a growing number of total HIV/AIDS cases in Ecuador. Over the 15 year period shown in Table 15, the number of cases will increase from 37,132 to 42,038, or 13 percent total increase (equivalent to annual average growth rate of 0.86 percent). The table also shows that the rate of under-reporting, initially at 71 percent in 2008, is expected to drop continuously through 2023, to reach a value of 37.9 percent. This projection is the result of a simple, yet empirically unsubstantiated assumption: that each year the absolute number of reported cases equals that of the previous year plus 5 percent of the previous year’s under-reported cases. In other words, it is assumed that under-reporting is absorbed into the reported cases at a constant annual rate of 5 percent. Figure 24 graphically presents the information contained in the table below.

Table 15 Projected evolution of the HIV/AIDS epidemic, 2008-2023

	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Total cases (C)	37.132	37.270	37.476	37.703	37.950	38.218	38.506	38.816	39.146	39.497	39.868	40.261	40.674	41.108	41.562	42.038
Reported cases (R)	10.765	12.083	13.343	14.549	15.707	16.819	17.889	18.920	19.915	20.876	21.807	22.710	23.588	24.442	25.276	26.090
Under-reported cases (U)	26.367	25.187	24.133	23.153	22.243	21.399	20.617	19.896	19.231	18.621	18.061	17.550	17.086	16.666	16.287	15.948
Under-reporting rate (%)	71,0%	67,6%	64,4%	61,4%	58,6%	56,0%	53,5%	51,3%	49,1%	47,1%	45,3%	43,6%	42,0%	40,5%	39,2%	37,9%

Annual absorption rate of under-reporting: 5%.

Figure 24 HIV/AIDS cases: total, reported, under-reported and under-reporting rate, 2008-2023 (number and percentage)

The following figure shows the expected consequence of a change in the ARV administration criterion. As can be seen, the combined effect of the ARV policy (both the CD4 count and its coverage) is a net drop in the projected number of PLWHA.

Figure 25 Simulation of the effect of a change in the criterion for ARV therapy on the projected number and prevalence of HIV/AIDS cases, 2008-2023 (cases and percent)

Further epidemiological information is presented in Table 16 for the Base Scenario. It includes the PLWHA and the projected prevalence if the ARV policy remained unchanged, then the same variables with a more aggressive ARV policy, the expected number of annual deaths, the mortality rate among the PLWHA, the persons in need of ARV therapy and, finally, those receiving the therapy.

7.2. Spending projections

Spending projections for the Base Demand Scenario are presented in Table 17. With the exception of the last spending category shown, “Other”, all other categories are those that in 2008 represented more than 1 percent of total spending in 2008. Together they accounted for 93 percent of total spending. The category “Other” lumps together all other spending items, with in 2008 amounted to about 7 percent of total spending.

According to the Base Demand Scenario, annual HIV/AIDS spending is expected to grow from US\$ 26.8 million in 2008 to US\$ 80.8 million in 2023, nearly a 200 percent increase. The projected spending share for the 7 largest spending categories is shown below in Figure 26.

Figure 26 Base Demand Scenario: Projected spending shares year 2023 (percent)

The above projections imply that total HIV/AIDS spending in the country will increase, both per citizen and per PLWHA (Figure 27). In 2008, these respective figures were US\$1.91 and US\$ 711. The model projects that by the year 2023 they will be US\$ 4.82 and US\$ 1,922.

Figure 27 Projected spending on HIV/AIDS, per citizen and per PLWHA, 2008-2023 (real US\$ of Dec. 2008)

Table 16 Epidemiological and treatment coverage historic information, 2000-2008, and projections, 2009-2023 (numbers and percentages)

	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	
Population (million)	12.3	12.5	12.5	12.8	13.0	13.2	13.4	13.6	13.8	14.0	14.2	14.4	14.6	14.8	15.0	15.2	15.4	15.6	15.8	16.0	16.2	16.4	16.6	16.8	
PLWHA (thousand)	36.3	36.4	36.4	36.5	36.6	36.7	36.8	36.9	37.1	37.3	37.5	37.7	37.9	38.2	38.5	38.8	39.1	39.5	39.9	40.3	40.7	41.1	41.6	42.0	
Prevalence (%)	0.30	0.29	0.29	0.28	0.28	0.28	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	
PLWHA after ARV treatment effect (thousand)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	37.1	37.2	37.4	37.6	37.8	38.1	38.3	38.5	38.8	39.1	39.4	39.7	40.0	40.3	40.6	40.8
Prevalence after ARV treatment effect (%)										0.27	0.27	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.24	0.24	
Newly reported HIV/AIDS cases	3.1	3.7	4.5	5.4	6.5	8.0	9.8	10.3	10.8	12.2	13.4	14.6	15.7	16.8	17.8	18.8	19.8	20.7	21.7	22.6	23.4	24.3	25.1	25.9	
Deaths from HIV/AIDS	245	357	395	422	495	618	699	649	679	728	781	836	892	948	1.005	1.064	1.123	1.131	1.139	1.147	1.156	1.165	1.173	1.181	
Mortality rate among PLWHA (%)	0.67	0.98	1.08	1.16	1.35	1.69	1.90	1.76	1.83	1.95	2.09	2.22	2.35	2.48	2.61	2.74	2.87	2.86	2.86	2.85	2.84	2.83	2.82	2.81	
Persons in need of ARV therapy (thousands)	6.1	6.4	6.6	6.7	6.9	7.1	7.4	7.8	8.6	16.4	18.8	21.3	23.9	26.5	29.2	31.9	34.8	37.8	39.5	41.2	42.8	44.3	45.8	47.3	
Persons receiving ARV therapy (thousands)	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.6	3.2	3.7	5.0	6.6	8.3	10.0	11.8	13.6	15.6	19.0	23.0	26.8	31.2	36.3	42.0	45.8	47.3	

Table 17 Demand for funding: Base Scenario with detailed costing information for largest cost items, 2008-2023 (million of real US\$ of Dec. 2008)

Spending category	Spending item	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Program management	Planning, coordination and management of the program	1.03	1.12	1.21	1.28	1.35	1.42	1.50	1.63	1.72	1.74	1.76	1.78	1.80	1.87	1.89	1.91
	Strengthening of the Administration and management of programs not unbundled by intervention	0.93	1.01	1.09	1.15	1.22	1.28	1.35	1.47	1.55	1.62	1.70	1.77	1.84	1.90	1.97	2.03
Prevention	Not disaggregated intervention prevention activities	5.51	5.99	6.51	7.08	7.70	8.37	9.10	9.90	10.03	10.16	10.29	10.42	10.55	10.67	10.79	10.91
	Communication for social change and behavioral health	0.97	1.03	1.08	1.14	1.20	1.27	1.34	1.41	1.43	1.45	1.46	1.48	1.50	1.52	1.54	1.55
	Programs for men who have sex with men	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.77	0.78	0.79	0.80	0.81	0.82	0.83	0.84
	Counseling and voluntary testing	0.70	0.71	0.73	0.74	0.76	0.77	0.79	0.80	0.81	0.82	0.83	0.84	0.86	0.87	0.88	0.88
	Prevention - Youth outside the educational system	0.48	0.61	0.76	0.96	1.21	1.52	1.92	2.41	2.44	2.48	2.51	2.54	2.57	2.60	2.63	2.66
	HIV transmission prevention for people living with HIV	0.45	0.49	0.53	0.58	0.63	0.68	0.74	0.81	0.85	0.89	0.93	0.97	1.01	1.05	1.08	1.12
	Programs for sex workers and their clients	0.43	0.44	0.44	0.44	0.44	0.44	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.46	0.47	0.47	0.48	0.48	0.49	0.49
	Universal precautions	0.41	0.44	0.48	0.52	0.57	0.62	0.67	0.73	0.74	0.75	0.76	0.77	0.78	0.79	0.80	0.81
	Community mobilization	0.30	0.33	0.36	0.39	0.42	0.46	0.50	0.55	0.55	0.56	0.57	0.57	0.58	0.59	0.60	0.60
Human resources	Monetary incentives for HR	0.49	0.53	0.58	0.61	0.64	0.68	0.71	0.77	0.82	0.85	0.89	0.93	0.97	1.00	1.04	1.07
Treatment and care	Treatment of opportunistic infections	7.05	7.67	8.34	8.79	9.27	9.77	10.30	11.21	11.80	11.80	12.33	12.85	13.32	13.78	14.25	14.72
	Outpatient	2.52	2.75	2.99	3.15	3.32	3.50	3.69	4.02	4.23	4.43	4.63	4.83	5.00	5.18	5.35	5.53
	First-line antiretroviral therapy	1.06	1.37	1.73	2.17	2.62	3.09	3.58	4.08	4.84	5.70	6.46	7.28	8.16	9.45	10.32	10.65
	Second-line antiretroviral therapy	0.95	1.43	2.08	2.61	3.16	3.72	4.31	4.91	6.37	8.19	10.13	12.47	15.28	17.70	19.31	19.94
	Not disaggregated care in hospital services	0.59	0.64	0.70	0.73	0.77	0.81	0.86	0.93	0.95	0.95	0.96	0.97	0.98	0.99	1.00	1.02
Other		1.78	1.94	2.12	2.27	2.43	2.62	2.82	3.11	3.24	3.37	3.49	3.60	3.72	3.83	3.94	4.04
Total		26.39	29.23	32.49	35.37	38.47	41.80	45.39	49.96	53.59	57.01	60.97	65.36	70.21	75.09	78.70	80.78

Table 18 Supply of funding: Base scenario, 2008-2023, (million of real US\$ of Dec. 2008)

Fuentes		2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Public sources	Treasury	20.69	20.69	21.69	22.45	23.88	25.05	26.28	27.57	28.92	30.34	31.83	33.38	35.00	36.69	38.45	40.30
	Mandatory employer social security contributions	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.10	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.12	0.13	0.14	0.14
	Mandatory worker social security contributions	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total public		20.76	20.76	21.77	22.52	23.97	25.14	26.37	27.66	29.02	30.45	31.94	33.50	35.12	36.82	38.59	40.44
Private sources	Households	1.82	1.83	1.83	1.84	1.86	1.87	1.88	1.89	1.90	1.92	1.93	1.95	1.96	1.98	1.99	2.00
	Firms	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	NGOs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total private		1.82	1.83	1.83	1.84	1.86	1.87	1.88	1.89	1.90	1.92	1.93	1.95	1.96	1.98	1.99	2.00
International sources	Global Fund	1.99	1.99	1.99	1.99	1.99	1.99	1.99	1.99	1.99	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Non profit international organizations	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	For profit international organizations	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total international		3.81	3.81	3.81	3.81	3.81	3.81	3.81	3.81	3.81	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total		26.39	26.40	27.41	28.18	29.64	30.82	32.06	33.37	34.74	32.42	33.88	35.45	37.09	38.80	40.58	42.44

Table 19 Demand and supply scenarios, 2009-2023 (million of real US\$ of Dec. 2008)

	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Demand															
D1	29.23	32.49	35.37	38.47	41.80	45.39	49.96	53.59	57.01	60.97	65.36	70.21	75.09	78.70	80.78
D2	29.04	32.15	34.95	37.92	41.11	44.55	48.85	52.53	56.02	60.03	64.51	69.48	74.46	78.22	80.38
D3	27.48	28.62	29.81	31.06	32.37	33.74	35.18	36.69	38.28	39.95	41.70	43.55	45.49	47.54	49.70
Supply															
O1	26.40	27.41	28.18	29.64	30.82	32.06	33.37	34.74	32.42	33.88	35.45	37.09	38.80	40.58	42.44
O2	27.40	28.17	29.62	30.81	32.05	33.35	34.73	39.39	44.23	49.73	56.00	63.13	71.25	80.50	91.02
O3	7.86	8.01	8.27	8.49	8.72	8.96	9.21	5.66	5.94	6.23	6.53	6.84	7.17	7.51	7.87

In the Base Scenario there is a considerable and growing future financing gap, as is shown in the following figure. By the year 2015 it will amount to US\$ 16.6 million, and by the year 2023 it will have grown to US\$ 38.2 million. In 2015 the gap will represent exactly one-third of total projected spending (US\$ 50 million, see Table 17). In 2023, the gap will have grown to account for 47.5 of projected spending.

Figure 28 Base Scenario: Projected gap between demand and supply of funding for HIV/AIDS, 2009-2023 (million real US\$ of Dec. 2008)

But the funding picture could be much worse, as is shown in the following table, which combines all scenarios to produce 9 gap calculations for each of three years, 2009, 2015, and 2023. As anticipated, the largest gap occurs when combining the Base Demand Scenario (D1) with the Pessimistic Supply Scenario (S3). By 2015 the gap would be US\$ 40.75 million and by 2023 it would grow to US\$ -72.91 million. The smallest gap scenarios are those that result from combining the Lower Coverage Demand Scenario (D3) with the Optimistic Supply Scenario (S2).

Table 20 Gap calculations, 2009, 2015, and 2023 (million of real US\$ of Dec. 2008)

Demand scenarios	Supply scenarios								
	2009			2015			2023		
	S1 Base	S2 Optimistic	S3 Pessimistic	S1 Base	S2 Optimistic	S3 Pessimistic	S1 Base	S2 Optimistic	S3 Pessimistic
D1 Base	-2.83	-1.82	-21.36	-16.60	-15.23	-40.75	-38.34	10.24	-72.91
D2 Efficiency	-2.64	-1.64	-21.18	-7.88	-6.52	-32.04	-37.94	10.64	-72.51
D3 Lower Coverage	-1.08	-0.08	-19.62	-1.81	-0.45	-25.97	-7.26	41.32	-41.83

8. Findings from the workshop

During the last week of August 2010 a workshop was held to present and discuss the results from the study in Ecuador. There was wide participation from the public and private sectors as well as from civil society. This workshop served to present the study results and receive comments in preparation for completing the study's final report. What follows is a summary account of what was done and said in the workshop.

The study's methods, conceptual framework, baseline assumptions and limitations were discussed. From this starting point the results were outlined with the information available from Ecuador. Comments from the audience were positive regarding the robustness of the model and the consistency of the results. Emphasis was placed on using the model as a valuable public policy tool, as well as for managing resources and developing empirical evidence to influence decision making.

The majority of the discussion during the workshop centered on the financing and demand gaps after 2015. These gaps are an important part of the projection model being used to identify the financing needs of the country in order to guarantee the provision of HIV/AIDS-related programming and the sources of financing until 2023. The main issue is to determine if available resources will be sufficient to finance the needed response to this epidemic. In the case that resources are insufficient to cover the next 15 years, it is important to identify alternate financing mechanisms to reduce the gap between supply of and demand for future resources.

Using the available data, the model predicts that there will likely be a funding gap and that it will be necessary to secure additional financing to close the gap. This conclusion could certainly come to pass if the HIV/AIDS epidemic turns out to be worse than currently expected, with an increased incidence and prevalence resulting in an increase in transmission of HIV. As a consequence, the country will need to respond to this increased demand with additional resources to try and close the gap. As such, it is important to identify disease control strategies.

This workshop highlighted the fact that public expenditure has increased in the past 3 years and it is hoped that it will be maintained in the future as a result of a constitutional mandate. One sign of the government's commitment to financing HIV/AIDS was the 29 percent increase in spending on HIV/AIDS in 2009, despite the global economic crisis and in the face of the country's mere 1 percent growth in GDP.

It is important to recognize that available funding does not cover all needs. This should be taken by officials in the country as a warning to take prompt action now. Early detection and timely treatment of HIV/AIDS cases, evaluation of the effectiveness of ARV drugs prior to commencing treatment and predictive analysis about viral resistance all contribute to reducing the probability of co-infections, complications and the need to use second- and third-line ARVs. Adopting this type of strategy may at first glance appear to be expensive, though in the long term it will translate into significant savings, and most importantly improve the quality of life, well-being and productive capacity of persons living with HIV.

There was general consensus about the decreasing tendency seen in external financing, which could signify an even greater reduction after 2015. Private support is limited and concentrated in a few pilot projects aimed at promoting rights of PLWH and HIV transmission prevention education.

It was noted that efficiency can play an important role in reducing the financing gap. Identification of efficient prevention strategies, early detection and timely treatment are important steps in improving HIV spending and closing the gap between supply of and demand for financial resources.

This study is an important tool for public policy making, in that it provides concrete, solid evidence about HIV/AIDS financing. In addition, the conceptual framework could be applied to other sectors for developing evidence-based public policy.

The model provides important information for identifying the areas needing strengthening and additional resources. In particular, it is necessary to develop strategies and courses of action for improving the efficiency of spending, which in the end will help close the financing gap. One example of this would be corporate purchase of ARV therapies. Additionally, ARV prices are constantly fluctuating as new active ingredients are introduced to respond to the mutations in the virus, which drives down the price of older drugs.

The emphasis on prevention as part of the response to HIV/AIDS could be more cost-effective if focused on the highest risk populations for transmission of HIV. As the epidemic grows amongst the young, men and women who have sex with men, the use of condoms grows to. This use can help reducing the transmission, although there are no known studies about the effectiveness of condom usage.

Regarding alternative financing mechanisms for the response to HIV/AIDS, it was mentioned that it is important to partner with the private sector, seeing as how this epidemic is not only a health problem but an intersectorial one which should include efforts and resources of both the public and private sectors. It is fundamental to involve private businesses through the corporate-social responsibility initiative.

One of the new financing mechanisms adopted in Ecuador is the conversion of external debt into local resources to invest in the national response to HIV/AIDS. Although this strategy channels resources directly to health, it represents the exit of external cooperation from the national scene in the medium-term.

It was suggested that local authorities could pass taxes earmarked for financing the HIV/AIDS response, for example charging the equivalent of US\$1 at establishments where sexual relations often occur, such as hotels, bars, nightclubs and saunas. This tax revenue could be invested, in these same establishments, in health promotion and HIV prevention campaigns including informational posters and access to condoms.

Strengthening tax policy will improve tax collection and given the government priority on this issue, result in increased financing for HIV/AIDS prevention and treatment. It was suggested that industries, like mining, that pose a health and environmental risk could be taxed. Tax exemptions, donations and other tax incentives could be established to generate additional funding for the HIV/AIDS response.

The option to tax international financial transactions for HIV/AIDS funding was also discussed. It was estimated that this option could generate a significant amount of funding, although in reality it would create significant policy, administrative and operational difficulties surrounding the collection and administration of the funds.

The development of intersectorial, multidisciplinary HIV/AIDS policies and programs in the workplace could help reduce the demand for financing and increase the efficiency of public health interventions.

It is important to put pressure on general social insurance, and increase the investment from police and the military in health promotion and HIV transmission prevention. Their involvement to date has been limited to diagnostic services and treatment of their beneficiaries.

9. Conclusions

This study built a model to project the future demand for and supply of funding for HIV/AIDS national response interventions and to determine whether there will be funding gaps. The demand for funding is expected to grow to enable Ecuador to face the challenge of improving the coverage for preventive and curative care for HIV/AIDS in order to fulfill the MDGs. An expected drop in external funding further complicates this challenge.

The study reveals that the effort made by the Ecuadorian government to strengthen the social public services is essential for covering the future growth in demand. Without the actual disbursement of resources, the supply of funding would have grown by 0.98 percent in 2009 instead of the significant 28.55 percent. The political will to support the health sector and in particular HIV/AIDS interventions made it possible to obtain positive gaps demonstrating the importance of public funding. The question is whether or not this effort will become sustainable and enacting public policy to ensure that funds are linked with current expenditure.

A projection of future demand and supply of funding reveals that in several of the projected scenarios a large funding gap is expected. New sources of funding, such as those mentioned in the workshop, or a growing fiscal effort by government, or sustained or greater financial support will be needed to bridge the projected gaps.

Annex A: HIV Prevention Tests

The HIV prevention testing is applied to three risk groups: pregnant women, MSM and CSW. Table 21 shows the percentage of testing performed by year and the number of people tested. From year 2016 onwards, 100 percent of the potential population will be tested.

Table 21 HIV Prevention testing 2010-2023

Year	Population	Population at risk	Tested population	% of applied tests
2010	14,204,900	427,823	213,912	50
2011	14,403,543	433,806	281,974	65
2012	14,602,471	439,797	351,838	80
2013	14,801,553	445,793	401,214	90
2014	15,000,661	451,790	429,200	95
2015	15,199,665	457,783	448,628	98
2016	15,399,757	463,810	463,810	100
2017	15,601,024	469,871	469,871	100
2018	15,801,677	475,915	475,915	100
2019	15,999,927	481,886	481,886	100
2020	16,193,984	487,730	487,730	100
2021	16,384,031	493,454	493,454	100
2022	16,571,261	499,093	499,093	100
2023	16,755,400	504,639	504,639	100

Source: Authors.

The test would reveal a total of 115,693 people living with HIV identified during the period 2010 – 2023, of which: 56,963 patients would get early ARV treatment; 45,571 opportunistic infections would be prevented; 227,853 hospitalizations and 90,047 HIV infections averted due to behavioral change of PLWHA. Table 22 shows the results.

Table 22 HIV preventive testing results

Year	HIV +	Patients with early ARV treatment	Number of opportunistic infections prevented	Prevented hospitalizations	Prevented HIV infections due to conduct modification
2010	4,123	1,845	1,476	7,381	3,209
2011	5,434	2,491	1,993	9,966	4,230
2012	6,781	3,183	2,546	12,731	5,278
2013	7,732	3,713	2,970	14,850	6,018
2014	8,272	4,056	3,245	16,223	6,438
2015	8,646	4,322	3,458	17,289	6,729
2016	8,939	4,469	3,575	17,877	6,957
2017	9,055	4,528	3,622	18,111	7,048
2018	9,172	4,586	3,669	18,344	7,139
2019	9,287	4,643	3,715	18,574	7,228
2020	9,400	4,700	3,760	18,799	7,316
2021	9,510	4,755	3,804	19,020	7,402
2022	9,619	4,809	3,847	19,237	7,486
2023	9,725	4,863	3,890	19,451	7,570
Total	115,693	56,963	45,571	227,853	90,047

Source: Authors.

Finally, is crucial to establish the costs of the preventive testing, estimate the potential savings and the social benefits that result with such strategy. The total savings during the period 2010 - 2023 due to prevented opportunistic infections, averted hospitalizations and HIV infections amount to US\$ 329,528,077, on the other hand the total cost of testing would be US\$ 220,075,922 resulting in a positive gap of US 109,452,155 (see Table 44).

Table 23 HIV preventive testing costs and benefits (US\$)

Year	Savings from prevented opportunistic infections	Savings from prevented hospitalizations	Savings from prevented HIV infections	Total savings	Annual detection cost	Gap
2010	95,956	369,060	15,475,842	15,940,857	7,841,996	8,098,862
2011	129,554	498,285	18,890,001	19,517,840	10,337,157	9,180,684
2012	165,504	636,555	21,825,732	22,627,792	12,898,368	9,729,424
2013	193,053	742,510	23,046,526	23,982,088	14,708,494	9,273,594
2014	210,900	811,152	22,829,314	23,851,365	15,734,481	8,116,885
2015	224,759	864,459	22,096,431	23,185,650	16,446,690	6,738,960
2016	232,403	893,858	22,854,222	23,980,484	17,003,263	6,977,220
2017	235,440	905,540	23,152,915	24,293,896	17,225,487	7,068,409
2018	238,469	917,187	23,450,697	24,606,353	17,447,033	7,159,320
2019	241,460	928,694	23,744,913	24,915,068	17,665,926	7,249,141
2020	244,389	939,958	24,032,906	25,217,253	17,880,189	7,337,064
2021	247,257	950,989	24,314,948	25,513,194	18,090,025	7,423,169
2022	250,083	961,856	24,592,809	25,804,748	18,296,751	7,507,998
2023	252,862	972,545	24,866,083	26,091,489	18,500,063	7,591,426
Total	2,962,088	11,392,648	315,173,341	329,528,077	220,075,922	109,452,155

Source: Authors.

Annex B: Workshop Participants List

Date: August 25, 2010

Nº	INSTITUTION	NAME	POSITION
1	Senpiades	Gabriela Guevara	S Y E
2	Unfpa	Llerena Freddy	Asesor
3	MSP	Susana Tamayo	Tecnico Vih
4	Kirima	Consuelo Herrera	Coord. M Y Z
5	Kirima	Amira Herdon	Directora
6	MSP	Fausto Patiño	Asesor
7	Fundación Clinton	Arturo Warleta	Representante
8	MCDS	Anabel Castillo	Analista Salud
9	MSP / PNS	Luis Morales	Jefe Pns
10	MSP /SEPSS	Nidia Rodriguez	Coordinadora
11	MSP / DCMSP	Ivan Moreira	Director
12	Unifen	Susana Flores	Coord. Renna
13	Equidad	Efrain Soria	Coordinador
14	Care	Silvia Tello	Consultora
15	MSP	Jorge Romero Correa	Analista De Proyecto
16	MSP	Americo Garrido	Asesor Tecnico
17	Conasa	Fausto Andrade	Coord. Tecnico
18	Unicef	Daniel Badilla	Consultor
19	Pnud / Pns	Doris Herrera	Coord. De Proyecto
20	Onusida	Juan Vasconez	Oficial Pais
21		Marcelo Morgano	Of Programa
22	MSP	Juana Cifuentes	Sev. Público
23	MSP / PNS	Leonor Ojeda	Tecnico Pns
24	OPS	Amaya Sanchez	